

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Review report for ENERGIZE+ business models' creation

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Executive Summary

The ENERGIZE project, co-funded by the European Commission under the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program, aims to foster the clean energy transition within European industrial sectors by establishing innovative cooperative energy models. With a consortium of nine multidisciplinary partners, including ICAEN, EAZK, IRIS, 3OC, ESTRATS, SYM, ENGREEN, EI-JKU, and FEDARENE, ENERGIZE leverages diverse expertise to ensure robust project implementation and broad replicability across Europe.

The project is set against the backdrop of the European Union's ambitious climate goals, including the EU Green Deal and the Fit for 55 plans, which aim for a 55% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030 and net-zero emissions by 2050. Industrial sectors, accounting for 37% of global energy consumption and 9.0 Gt of CO₂ emissions in 2022 [1], represent both a challenge and an opportunity for the clean energy transition.

Thus, ENERGIZE aims to promote the global adoption of sustainable industrial energy practices. By demonstrating the potential of Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs) through its pilots and sharing replicable tools, the project aims to make a significant contribution to reducing carbon CO₂ and promoting a cleaner, more resilient energy future.

To address the main project objective, ENERGIZE focuses on addressing these challenges by creating IRECs within selected industrial zones in city of Manresa (Spain), Valesia Region (Italy), Zlín Region (Czech Republic), and Upper Austria (Austria). These pilot projects aim to demonstrate the feasibility of cooperative energy models, achieving significant carbon reductions and fostering sustainable industrial practices.

Within the project logical framework, this report is part of the WP2 and implements the Task 2.2, having the ambition of providing the necessary instruments for performing an analysis of the ENERGIZE application in industrial sector in the target countries and then identifying the most robust and replicable Business Models (BMs).

The overall approach of the study is founded on strong understanding of the State of the Art of the sector of intervention. The study is performed by (i) reviewing official report, documents, literature and (ii) involving stakeholders to gather updated information. Defining benchmarks is approached not only by studying the market in its general terms (macroeconomics, regulation, sizing, financing, etc.), but focusing on adopted business models, which are chosen as the key tool for identifying barriers and opportunities in the reference market.

The review of the **legal and regulatory framework** and financial mechanisms highlights both strengths and gaps within the European context and individual Member States. While current regulations and incentives are strongly oriented towards supporting the energy transition, they often favour small-scale configurations and leave room for improvement in supporting large-scale initiatives within industrial parks.

Greater regulatory harmonisation across European countries could facilitate the adoption of cooperative models on a larger scale, reducing disparities in access to incentives and simplifying administrative requirements. In addition, targeted financial instruments tailored to the specific needs of industrial parks could accelerate the energy transition by promoting solutions such as energy storage and shared resource management.

To maximise the impact of energy transition initiatives, it will be crucial to continue fostering cooperation between stakeholders, investing in advanced technological tools and strengthening institutional support. These elements will help ensure greater replicability of the models and consolidate the results achieved, inspiring other industrial sectors to follow similar paths.

The **analysis of financing mechanisms** across the European Union reveals barriers and opportunities in supporting the development of IRECs. While funding programs are all fully aligned with the EU's goals for decarbonization and energy transition, their accessibility, scope, and implementation vary significantly, reflecting differences in regional priorities, economic contexts, and financial strategies.

Despite existing barriers, several opportunities can enhance the effectiveness of financing mechanisms for renewable energy projects and IRECs and could accelerate the development of sustainable energy systems and ensure that financial mechanisms deliver equitable and impactful results across EU.

Among several opportunities, the most relevant ones are (1) Alternative financing mechanisms like crowdlending and equity crowdfunding, (2) Tailored financial programs to be set starting on ongoing ones to support high-power capacity IRECs, (3) European-Level Funding Programs focused on green transitions and regional development (4) Capacity-building initiatives to enhance IREC groups to better leverage available resources.

Even if strong opportunities are identified in all the four target countries, (Italy, Spain, Austria and Czech Republic), several barriers are still persistent at both EU and country level, such as (1) main focus on small-scale projects only, (2) administrative complexity, which discourages participation, particularly for SMEs and energy communities, (3) regional and economic disparities, especially in less economically developed regions, (4) investment risks due to regulatory changes, high initial costs and long payback periods, (5) limited crowdfunding options, (6) weak EU-level coordination, which is desired to harmonize strategies across Member States, reducing regional disparities and enhancing the overall efficiency of funding mechanisms.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
ARERA	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente
BM	Business Model
DSM	Demand-side management
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
EED	Energy Efficiency
EIB	European Investment Bank
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESG	Environmental, Social, Governance
EU	European Union
EU ETS	EU Emission Trading System
FEIS	European Fund for Strategic Investment
FFR	Recovery and Resilience Facility
GLP	Green Loan Principles
GSE	Gestore dei Servizi Energetici
GHG emissions	Greenhouse Gas Emission
ICO	Instituto de Credito Oficial
IREC	Industrial Renewable Energy Community
JTF	Just Transition Fund
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MASE	Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica
MIMIT	Ministero delle Imprese e del Made in Italy
NZT	Net Zero Emission

PNRR	Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SET Plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
VAT	Valu-Added Tax
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction and Objectives

ENERGIZE project is funded by the European Union, under the LIFE program, and it is coordinated by IRIS. The Consortium is composed of 9 multidisciplinary partners, including 2 regional agencies (ICAEN, EAZK), 5 expert companies in energy sector (IRIS, 3OC, ESTRATS, SYM, ENGREEN), 1 research organization (EIJKU), and a European federation of agencies (FEDARENE) and regions for energy environment ensuring replicability across EU.

Policy initiatives, such as the European Green Deal (in 2020) and the Fit for 55 plan (in 2021), which aim for a 55% cut in CO₂ emissions by 2030 (from 1990 levels) and for net-zero emissions by 2050 are supporting Europe leadership in energy transition. However, many EU countries are net importers of oil and gas (in 2022 the EU's natural gas import dependency rate was 97%), and thus particularly exposed to energy reliability and market volatility risks.

Europe's industrial sector stands as a pivotal player in the regional and global landscape, accounting for a substantial portion of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. The statistics tell (in 2022) that this sector represented 37% of global energy use, a notable increase from the 34% recorded in 2002. This growth in energy consumption primarily stems from energy intensive subsectors within the industry.

While industrialization has been pivotal in Europe's economic development, it has also been accompanied by significant environmental costs. In 2022, the industrial sector alone was responsible for emitting a staggering 9.0 Gt of CO₂. To put this into perspective, this translates to roughly one-quarter of global energy system CO₂ emissions. Although modest improvements have been achieved in terms of energy efficiency and the adoption of renewable energy sources, the pace of progress remains notably slow. To align with the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 (NZE) Scenario, a substantial reduction in industrial emissions to approximately 7 Gt CO₂ by 2030 is imperative [2].

To align with the NZE by 2050 Scenario, Energy Communities have emerged as a promising solution, although they remain uncommon in industrial areas. The ENERGIZE project, which has been designed by a leading multidisciplinary team of researchers, regional and EU level agencies and expert companies from the energy sector, stands as a pioneering initiative to tackle the challenges experienced by the industrial sector, demonstrating the feasibility of creating Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs) using cooperative energy models. In order to ensure access to and replicability of the project outputs, the training and capacity building tools developed in the project will be digitized and made available through a community-based Digital Hub for professionals interested in energy communities and collaborative energy models, who will benefit from an acceleration program that will have been tested and validated in our 4 pilot industrial zones, the KPIs from which will be tracked and widely disseminated.

In this context, the ENERGIZE project seeks to demonstrate the feasibility of cooperative energy models in selected EU industrial zones (Manresa, Catalonia; Valesia Region, Italy; Zlín Region, Czech Republic; Upper Austria, Austria) by fostering energy collaboration. With a focus on significant carbon reduction, thanks to its pilots and compelling KPIs in terms of company participation, training and skills development, energy savings, renewable energy generation, GHG emissions reduction, job creation, as well as its impacts for policy making and stakeholder outreach, the project aims to inspire global adoption of sustainable industrial energy practices. The ENERGIZE project has the ambition to serve as a catalyst for sustainable industrial energy cooperation, inspiring other regions to embrace similar models, with a vision to make a substantial contribution to the global reduction of carbon emissions and the promotion of sustainable energy practices on a global scale.

This report is part of the WP2 and implements the Task 2.2, having the ambition of providing the necessary instruments for performing an analysis of the ENERGIZE application in the industrial sector in the target countries and then identifying the most robust and replicable Business Models (BMs).

1.1 Overview of Energy Cooperation definitions in European Urban-Industrial Parks

This section provides a concise overview of key definitions relevant to energy cooperation and energy communities, drawing from Deliverable 2.1 (Subsection 2.5) of the ENERGIZE project. These definitions establish a foundational framework for the subsequent chapters, which explore the legislative and financial mechanisms specifically designed for Renewable Energy Communities (REC) constituted by companies—referred to as Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs). Given the project's focus on fostering sustainable energy practices within industrial zones, it is essential to introduce these concepts to better understand the policies and strategies discussed later.

1.1.1 Energy Cooperation definitions

Energy cooperation is defined as a collaborative approach to sustainable energy solutions, encompassing the production, procurement and consumption of energy among multiple stakeholders. This cooperation aims to optimize energy demand and improve sustainability by pooling resources and fostering partnerships. Examples include shared energy production plants, district heating systems and waste heat recovery within industrial parks or between industrial companies and surrounding communities.

A key aspect of energy cooperation is its alignment with **industrial symbiosis**, which focuses on resource exchange among companies. Energy cooperation serves as a subset of this concept, specifically targeting energy-related activities such as joint procurement, shared infrastructure and knowledge exchange. These collaborations often occur in geographically localized settings, involving stakeholders from various sectors, including SMEs, local authorities and utility providers.

Trust and robust communication are critical to the success of energy cooperation. Effective coordination ensures optimized resource use, enhanced energy efficiency and shared value creation, yielding both environmental and financial benefits. However, energy cooperation remains a relatively rare practice, with challenges such as heterogeneous project characteristics, varying energy needs and differing levels of trust between stakeholders.

1.1.2 Comparison between Energy Cooperation and Energy Communities

While energy cooperation and energy communities share a collective approach to energy management, their frameworks differ. Energy cooperation lacks a formal legal structure within European energy policies, whereas energy communities, such as **Renewable Energy Communities (REC)** and **Citizen Energy Communities (CEC)**, are supported by specific regulations under the EU's Clean Energy Package. Specifically:

- **Renewable Energy Communities (REC):** Defined by the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II), RECs are autonomous legal entities based on voluntary participation, focused on local renewable energy projects. They prioritize environmental, economic and social benefits over financial profits and operate within a limited geographical scope.
- **Citizen Energy Communities (CEC):** Defined by the International Electricity Market Directive (IEMD), CECs also emphasize collective energy actions but are not limited by geographical proximity. Their operations focus on electricity generation and involve participants like natural persons, local authorities, and SMEs.

Despite their differences, both RECs and CECs aim to facilitate the clean energy transition through collective energy production, distribution and consumption. These models represent structured, regulated approaches to energy collaboration, in contrast to the broader and less formalized scope of energy cooperation.

By understanding these distinctions, stakeholders in urban-industrial parks can better identify opportunities to adopt cooperative or community-based energy models that align with their specific needs and contexts.

2 Methodology

2.1 Desk Research on general terms of Market Analysis

Task T2.2 has been carried out via remote work by the task leader EnGreen Srl, in close collaboration with other three project partners: ICAEN, 3OC, EI-JKU.

In particular, the Task activities leverage from other Tasks and related outputs and deliverables, specifically start from:

- a broader Market Analysis [T2.1], which is necessary for the full understanding of the context and is based on a step-by-step methodology (see Table I), which is fully focused on analysing the Urban - Industrial Park Energy cooperation initiatives.
- a stakeholder and energy cooperative user research [T3.2]. The task aims at identifying critical needs, skill gaps, and often overlooked challenges faced by the stakeholders. This will be achieved by 1) analysing skills gaps in training, 2) aligning priorities and needs, and 3) identifying and addressing barriers, including those related to policy, perception, economics, and technical factors associated with energy cooperation. This will be done through desktop research, interviews and surveys. The output of this task will be detailed personas (user profiles) with its related capacity building needs, pains and priorities.)

This task is devoted to the exploration of how ENERGIZE can become a catalyst for sustaining the industrial sector in Europe. RECs are looking at the promotion of decarbonizing energy systems and ensuring a more sustainable and locally produced energy resources, limiting fossil fuels usage. For this reason, the identification of key financial schemes able to boost this transition may help communities in accelerating in this green revolution.

The task objective aims to investigate the market readiness of the ENERGIZE business models in RECs, to establish a comprehensive understanding of how ENERGIZE can empower the industrial parks environment and provide stakeholders and practitioners with reference figures.

Thus, this task deals with a focus on the business models and financial schemes, including a specific stakeholder consultation, to explore the legal and socioeconomical requirements for innovative cooperation models adopting ENERGIZE support in industrial park initiatives. The study includes a full analysis of the enabling environment, including financing bodies and instruments for a strong project viability as well as environmental and social implications for a long-term project sustainability. The market readiness is verified through business modelling on case studies representing typical applications in different contexts of interventions.

The methodology is summed up in the following flowchart, representing eight key phases it is composed of:

- [T2.2.a] Validation of Table of Contents for deliverables [D2.2]
- [T2.2.b] Inserting relevant contents from Input Deliverables
- [T2.2.c] Desk research to implement missing contents on market analysis (excluding business models)
- [T2.2.d] Review of existing financial mechanism, regulatory framework and business models for industrial parks
- [T2.2.e] Review of existing financial mechanism, regulatory framework and business models in energy cooperatives
- [T2.2.f] Identification of potential financial mechanism and business models to integrate industrial parks & energy cooperatives (to be validated in next WP)
- [T2.2.g] Draft version of D2.2
- [T2.2.h] Gathering comments from WP partners on Draft D2.2
- [T2.2.i] Final version of D2.2

Task 2.2 analyses the current financial instruments for the industrial sector, having a specific focus on European context (with particular attention to Italy, Spain, Czech Republic and Austria).

In particular, the following different elements are analysed:

- Key actors in the energy financial sector
- Policy and regulatory framework
- Financial supporting mechanisms

Task 2.2 is to comprehensively understand the REC sector to assess potential business models and propose sustainable mechanisms for promoting ENERGIZE business models in the reference context. However, it must be intended as a “light” analysis mostly because it is carried out only via remote research, with limited interactions with local stakeholders. Thus, methods adopted are the following:

- Desk research of official reports, scientific literature and websites.
- Analysis of the key actors' background.
- Direct online consultation with key actors.

This Phase aims also to analyse the current State of the Art of the industrial cooperation initiatives, having a specific focus on European applications for REC.

The intention is to establish which are the requirements of an area or of a community to create the best synergies between ENERGIZE business models and Industrial Energy Communities. Each of the proposed models includes unique features to be observed for significantly improving profitability and thus for justifying any investment costs.

This Phase leverages a full understanding of the Industrial sector to categorize all the ENERGIZE potential applications in different REC types to perform a detailed analysis of selected applications and thus provide simulations of Business Model (BM) full feasibility studies. Green financing and tailor-made financial products for citizens and industrial energy cooperative requirements are considered, as well as the identification of potential business models already implemented.

The first steps include a **benchmarking analysis** of the success stories of energy cooperatives in Spain, Austria, the Czech Republic and Italy. Once the background has been overviewed, the business model classification based on service provided, operating method, ownership and other relevant aspects belonging to the Use Cases of the ENERGIZE Project is carried out. The **definition of value propositions** is one of the key processes in defining business models.

The contemporary step is the pursuit of a **financial analysis** of different business models. To foster community engagement is pivotal, the research for **synergies among industrial and residential sectors is pivotal**. Particularly, a focus is planned on:

- Customer management and payment systems.
- Complementary activities.
- Investing in local communities to enhance project bankability and sustainability
- Assessing the Social Return on Investment

Then, technical requirements and demand management strategies are at the basis for the **technical analysis of the energy cooperatives**. Finally, an in-depth study on **new trends in Green Financing** coupled with an evaluation on **business barriers and opportunities** provides a complete and clear picture of the all-round development of the projects under consideration

Special attention should be paid to **Financing Instruments**, to which a dedicated analysis is devoted. This analysis includes a mapping of relevant financial instruments given the specific national and local context, as well as stakeholders' needs and requirements. To obtain relevant results, it is necessary to go over the following topics:

- Overview of financing institutions and bodies.
- Support scheme and instruments for energy cooperatives
- Alternative sources of financing
- Financing barriers and opportunities

3 Legal and Regulatory framework

Within the broader EU regulatory framework for Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) which reflects the EU's commitment to decarbonization and the energy transition, as outlined in the “Green Deal” and “Fit for 55” targets, with the aim to promote cooperative energy models and improve energy efficiency, this chapter reports highlights given by deep-dive research to explore the most recent legislative developments at the **European Union** high-level as well as in **Italy, Spain, Austria, and the Czech Republic**.

The analysis focuses on IRECs across the above target areas and exclusively on the related latest regulations, as they consolidate or replace older ones, which are no longer valid or have expired. This approach ensures the content remains focused on the most up-to-date frameworks, providing stakeholders with a comprehensive overview for understanding the current legal and regulatory frameworks.

Key aspects of each law/regulation are summarized as follows:

- **Policy/Directive/Law/Regulation:** the name of the act analysed
- **Topic:** the full title of the law or, if unavailable, a concise summary of the regulation's primary focus.
- **Brief Description:** a short explanation of the regulation, highlighting its purpose, scope, and relevance to energy communities.
- **Key Stakeholders:** the main groups or entities impacted by or involved in the regulation.
- **Funding Type:** the mechanisms or sources of financial support associated with the Policy/Directive/Law/Regulation, if applicable.
- **Assessment of the potential gaps:** a critical evaluation of the regulation's limitations or challenges in its implementation, with particular attention to IRECs.

This structure allows for easy comparison across countries and highlights areas where harmonization or further improvements could support the development of IRECs.

The goal of this chapter is to identify best practices, regulatory gaps, and financial mechanisms that can help stakeholders navigate the legal environment and design successful business models for IRECs.

The analysis of the regulatory frameworks across Italy, Spain, Austria and the Czech Republic reveals both strengths and challenges in the development of IRECs. While all countries align with the EU's goals for decarbonization and energy transition, their approaches and implementations vary significantly, reflecting differences in national priorities, economic structures and legislative maturity.

Strengths:

- **Italy** has a robust regulatory framework that encourages renewable energy use through incentives like feed-in tariffs and tax credits. However, its focus on small-scale configurations (<1 MW) and municipalities with fewer than 5,000 residents limits the applicability to larger industrial parks.
- **Spain** offers a flexible framework for RECs, emphasizing local participation and resilience. Yet, geographic and technical restrictions could hinder broader adoption in industrial contexts.
- **Austria** demonstrates a mature framework with comprehensive support for RECs. Its Renewable Energy Expansion Act (EAG) provides a solid foundation for IRECs, though specific measures targeting industrial applications remain limited.

- **The Czech Republic** is progressively integrating energy communities into its legislative framework. However, administrative burdens and infrastructure costs pose significant barriers, particularly for smaller entities.

However, several challenges emerge across these countries. The regulations often focus more on residential or small-scale projects rather than larger industrial contexts, leaving gaps in support for industrial parks. The lack of clear definitions and standards for IRECs creates obstacles for collaboration between countries and makes it harder to replicate successful initiatives. Additionally, high initial investment costs and complex administrative requirements discourage widespread adoption, particularly for smaller companies or projects in less developed regulatory environments.

The differences in approaches provide opportunities for countries to learn from each other and adopt best practices. More coordination at the European level, together with incentives tailored to industrial settings, could fill many of these gaps. Simplifying administrative procedures and offering financial support for large-scale projects would also accelerate the development of IRECs.

Finally, while the existing regulations offer a good starting point, further standardization and targeted measures are essential to fully realize the potential of IRECs in industrial areas. Aligning policies with practical needs will help to ensure that these frameworks effectively support sustainable energy transitions across Europe.

3.1 European Union

Table 3-1 EU legal and regulatory framework

Policy/Directive	Topic	Brief Description	Key Stakeholders	Funding Type	Assessment on potential gaps
Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) (2012) (amended on 2023) [3]	Energy Efficiency Directive (2023) and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955	Aims to improve energy efficiency by 32.5% by 2030. Targets energy savings across buildings, industries, public sectors, and energy systems to reduce consumption and improve efficiency.	EU member states, businesses, energy consumers, industries, and public authorities.	EU funds (2021-2027 framework and Recovery and Resilience Facility), InvestEU Program, European Investment Bank (EIB) financing, project bonds, credit guarantees, energy performance contracts, third-party financing systems, and training programs.	Variable implementation among Member States; financial constraints for SMEs in energy communities (CERs); frequent regulatory changes create investment uncertainty.
Renewable Energy Directive (RED II (2018) & III (2023))	Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources	Sets binding targets for renewable energy (32% by 2030 under RED II, 42,5% under RED III) and focuses on energy communities, decentralised energy production and integration of renewables into the energy system.	EU member states, energy producers, energy communities (IRECs), industries and local authorities.	Feed-in tariffs, subsidies, grants, and other national and EU-level support mechanisms for renewable energy projects.	National targets vary, causing disparities in commitment; inconsistent support schemes for energy communities; bureaucratic obstacles discourage local initiatives; limited market access for small energy producers; economic risks linked to energy price volatility and investment costs.
Electricity Market Directive (2019/944) [4]	Concerning common rules for the internal market in electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU	Establishes common rules for electricity generation, transmission, distribution and supply while promoting competitive, decentralized and consumer-driven markets. Focuses on empowering CECs	CEC, small producers, energy consumers, renewable energy cooperatives and distributed energy systems.	Financing from the European Investment Bank (EIB) and other European financial institutions, national and regional funds supported by revenues from emission trading schemes, credit guarantees, energy performance contracts and third-party financing	Primarily targets residential and small-scale producers; limited direct guidelines for industrial applications. Implementation and adaptation vary by Member State.
Clean Energy for All Europeans (2019) [5]	The package will help to decarbonize EU's energy system in line with the European Green Deal objectives.	Legislative package aimed at modernizing the EU energy system, integrating renewables, increasing energy storage capacity, and enhancing interconnection between Member States.	EU energy producers, grid operators, consumers and local authorities.	EU budget allocation (20-25% for climate measures), Horizon Europe (R&I in energy and climate), Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan), Juncker Plan (leveraging public funds for private investment), and European Fund for Strategic Investments (FEIS).	Complex administrative procedures may discourage companies, especially SMEs.

European Green Deal (2019) [6]	To become the first climate neutral continent	The EU's overarching strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, focusing on emissions reduction, renewable energy, and the circular economy. Covers climate, energy, transport, agriculture, biodiversity, and pollution.	EU member states, industries, businesses, citizens, and public authorities.	EU funding programs, investments in renewable energy, and climate action projects (e.g., Horizon Europe, Recovery and Resilience Facility, etc).	Requires substantial alignment and coordinated action across all sectors and Member States to address disparities in commitment, resources, and implementation capacities.
Fit for 55 Package (2021) [7]	Climate neutrality by 2050 and a 55 % reduction of net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030, compared with 1990 levels	A package of measures aimed at reducing EU greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, aligning policies and regulations with the EU Green Deal. Updates existing regulations and introduces new ones to achieve the Green Deal's objectives.	EU member states, businesses, energy producers, industries.	Not a direct funding law; however, the package includes implications for funding mechanisms like Horizon Europe, InvestEU, EU ETS, Green Bonds, and the Recovery and Resilience Facility.	Fit for 55 requires substantial financial and regulatory efforts, which could prove difficult to implement without clear policies and adequate investments.

3.2 Italy

Table 3-II Italian legal and regulatory framework

Law /Regulation	Topic	Brief Description	Key Stakeholders	Funding Type	Assessment of potential gaps
"Conto Termico" (DM 28-12-2012, amended on 16-02-2016) [8]	Encouragement of thermal energy production from renewable sources and small-scale energy efficiency measures.	Supports renewable heating systems for self-consumption and energy efficiency, including in industrial contexts, through incentives for thermal energy production from renewable sources like solar thermal, biomass, and heat pumps.	Businesses, municipalities, and private entities with renewable heating systems.	Grants for renewable thermal systems, including solar thermal and biomass.	Primarily focused on thermal energy and small to medium-scale projects, not applicable to large-scale industrial operations.
Millerproghe decree No. 162/2019 [9]	Urgent provisions on the extension of legislative deadlines, the organisation of public administrations and technological innovation.	Extends deadlines and updates regulations to promote local renewable energy generation and self-consumption models.	Renewable energy producers (individual and collective), SMEs, local authorities, and public institutions.	Grants based on self-consumed energy within RECs, limited to municipalities <5,000 residents.	Initially restricted to systems <200 kW, later expanded to 1 MW; primarily applicable in low-voltage contexts.
Decree "Semplificazioni" No. 120/2020 [10]	Urgent measures for simplification and digital innovation	Simplifies administrative procedures for renewable energy projects, especially in the renewable sector, to speed up approval and installation processes.	Renewable energy project developers.	Enables access to public funds (European, national, regional, chamber-level) by streamlining processes.	Implementation depends on local and regional plans; disparities in application may cause delays in certain areas.

Decree No. 199/2021 [11]	Implementation of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (REDII) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.	Promotes decentralized renewable energy production, encouraging self-consumption and energy sharing via RECs in low and medium-voltage settings.	Municipalities (<5,000 residents), local authorities, SMEs, industries, and renewable energy producers.	Grants (only for municipalities with a population <5000 inhabitants) and Incentive tariffs through GSE for renewable energy production.	Incentives are limited to municipalities with <5000 residents, reducing industrial park applicability.
ARERA Resolution 727/2022 [12]	Definition of the regulation of diffuse auto-consumption. approval of the integrated diffuse self-consumption text	Regulates self-consumption and RECs in line with Legislative Decree 199/2021, introducing provisions on shared energy and incentives for renewable energy production.	Grouped self-consumers (condominiums, public buildings), RECs, SMEs, industries, and public authorities.	Same as DL 199/2021: Provides incentives via GSE for shared energy.	Limited to low-voltage systems; participants shall be geographically close; installation size <1 MW.
Decree TIAD CER 2024 [13]	Decree TIAD (Integrated Text on Diffuse Self-Consumption) CER (REC)	Defines regulatory conditions for REC, collective self-consumption and prosumers, promoting shared renewable energy use, especially in collective self-consumption projects	RECs, citizens' groups, individual prosumers, SMEs, and public institutions.	Grants and support scheme for energy sharing projects, limited to municipalities <5000 residents.	Primarily targets low voltage systems with limited applicability for industrial parks.
Decree FER 2 (DM 19-06-2024, amended on 10-12-2024) [14]	Incentives for innovative or high-cost renewable energy plants with innovative characteristics and low environmental and territorial impact.	Promotes renewable electricity generation, focusing on high-cost and innovative renewable energy technologies like floating offshore wind, advanced geothermal and marine energy sources.	Renewable energy producers.	Incentives awarded through competitive auctions and feed-in tariffs.	Primarily applies to innovative and high-cost renewable technologies; focuses on new plants rather than existing installations. Excludes traditional onshore photovoltaic systems.
Regional Law "Piemonte" 12/2018 [15]	Regional Law for the Promotion of the Establishment of Energy Communities	Promotes the establishment and operation of RECs in Piedmont by public and private entities.	Public and private entities.	Financial support for the establishment phase of energy communities, specifically for project development and preparatory documentation, with criteria and modalities defined by the Regional Council.	Energy communities shall allocate at least 70% of the energy produced for self-consumption by members to maintain producer status. Communities failing to meet strategic objectives lose access to regional, national, or EU funding for up to two years, until compliance is restored.

3.3 Spain

Table 3-III Spanish legal and regulatory framework

Law /Regulation	Topic	Brief Description	Key Stakeholders	Funding Type	Assessment of potential gaps
Real Decreto 244/2019 [16]	Regulates the administrative, technical and economic conditions for the self-consumption of electricity.	Establishes conditions for electricity self-consumption, including technical and administrative rules for self-consumption systems (individual and collective), and energy compensation for surplus.	Self-consumers, including individuals and groups participating in shared energy generation and consumption.	Surplus compensation, tax benefits	Technical limitations for installations over 100 kW; required documentation for grid connection
Real Decreto 1183/2020 [17]	Law to access and connection to electricity transmission and distribution networks.	Establishes criteria and procedures for access and connection to the electricity grid, promoting renewable energy projects and self-consumption.	Community energy operators, energy companies, distribution and transmission entities	State funding for connection infrastructure and incentives for renewable energy projects	Technical barriers to connection, capacity limits, and transparency requirements for infrastructures
Real Decret 24/2021 (Catalonia) [18]	Transposes EU directives on covered bonds, cross-border distribution of collective investment undertakings, open data and re-use of public sector information, the exercise of copyright and related rights applicable to certain online transmissions and retransmissions of radio and television programs, temporary exemptions for certain imports and supplies, for consumers and for the promotion of clean and energy-efficient road transport vehicles.	Accelerates the deployment of distributed and participatory renewable energy, focusing on community participation in renewable energy projects.	Owners of renewable energy installations, local communities, and businesses participating in CERs.	Not specified	Installations only on roofs or urban areas; exclusion of projects with significant environmental impact
Orden TED/1247/2021 [19]	Law for the implementation of variable distribution coefficients in collective self-consumption collective	Regulate variable sharing coefficients for collective self-consumption, improving efficiency in the distribution of locally generated energy	Participants in collective self-consumption projects, including citizens, SMEs, and local cooperatives	State and local incentives for implementing energy self-consumption projects	Administrative complexity for setting up and communicating coefficients
Law 23/2020 (as amended by Law 8/2023) [20]	Adopts energy and other measures for economic recovery.	Introduces RECs into Spanish legislation, promoting local	Renewable energy producers, SMEs, local communities, and public	Grants for renewable energy projects, resilience programs (e.g., InvestEU),	Geographic proximity for participation in RECs; non-profit

		participation in the energy transition. Simplifies administrative processes and ensures economic resilience for energy systems.	authorities participating in energy transition projects.	and competitive mechanisms for renewable energy remuneration.	nature of REC restricts profit distribution.
Real Decreto 5/2023 [21]	Law for adopting and extending certain measures in response to the economic and social consequences of the war in Ukraine, to support the reconstruction of the island of La Palma and other situations of vulnerability, to transpose European Union directives on structural changes in commercial companies and to reconcile family and working life for parents and carers, and to implement and enforce European Union law.	Promote CECs and RECs to foster energy transition, reduce energy costs, and improve efficiency	Citizens, SMEs, cooperatives, public and private entities, particularly in vulnerable areas	Next Generation EU funds, state incentives for local renewable projects	Complex regulations, technical and geographic requirements for accessing incentives

3.4 Austria

Table 3-IV Austrian legal and regulatory framework

Law/Regulation	Topic	Brief Description	Key Stakeholders	Funding Type	Assessment of potential gaps
Electricity Industry and Organization Act (EIWOG 2010) (amended on 22/10/2013) [22]	Federal Act Providing New Rules for the Organisation of the Electricity Sector	Ensures high-quality electricity at reasonable prices, promotes renewable energy, guarantees safety, supply security, and environmental compatibility, including participation in RECs, framework conditions for CECs, and guaranteed access to the grid for renewable energy producers and REC members under fair and non-discriminatory terms. Includes conditions for energy measurement and billing.	All electricity consumers in Austria, with a focus on increasing renewable energy production	Does not offer direct funding for renewable energy projects but ensures a supportive framework for their integration	General provisions for the electricity market; does not specifically address RECs or industrial parks
Energy Control Act (E-ControlG)(2014) [23]	Federal Act on the Regulatory Authority in the Electricity and Natural Gas Industries (Energy Control Act - E-ControlG)	Establishes the regulatory framework for electricity and natural gas industries in Austria, ensuring compliance with EU directives and fostering market transparency, indirectly supporting renewable energy integration and community models like RECs.	Public and private sector participants in the electricity and natural gas industries, including renewable energy producers	Not directly focused on funding; supports a regulatory environment for market functioning	Primarily focuses on market regulation and transparency; lacks direct measures or incentives specific to RECs

Renewable Energy Expansion Act (EAG) (2021) [24]	Federal Act on the Expansion of Energy from Renewable Sources (Renewable Energy Expansion Act)	Promotes renewable electricity and gas generation, regulates RECs, and incentivizes hydrogen and gas projects to achieve Austria's climate neutrality by 2040, including subsidies for RECs.	Renewable energy producers, RECs, local authorities, SMEs, and households	Feed-in premiums, investment grants, and auctions for renewable energy projects	Focuses on general renewable energy projects; limited specific measures for industrial RECs
Green Electricity Act (2012) (amended on 2024) [25]	Federal Act on the Promotion of Electricity Generation from RE sources	Supports renewable electricity production via feed-in tariffs, investment grants, and efficiency bonuses, focusing on hydropower, wind, photovoltaic, biomass, and biogas sectors.	Renewable energy producers, including participants in RECs	Feed-in tariffs, subsidies, and investment grants for renewable electricity projects	Primarily focuses on large-scale installations; limited direct applicability to small or industrial RECs

3.5 Czech Republic

Table 3-V Czech legal and regulatory framework

Policy/Regulation	Topic	Brief Description	Key Stakeholders	Funding Type	Assessment of potential gaps
Energy Act No. 458/2000 (as amended by Act No. 469/2023 and Lex OZE II) [26]	Act on the Conditions of Business and the Exercise of State Administration in Energy Sectors and on Amendments to Certain Acts	Establishes the regulatory framework for energy production, transmission, distribution, and trade, with updates including definitions and provisions for energy communities and renewable resource communities.	Energy producers, energy communities, cooperatives, SMEs, local authorities, and market operators.	Not specified	Complex registration for energy communities; non-network infrastructure fees require detailed reporting and compliance, increasing administrative and cost burdens, especially for smaller entities.

4 Financial instruments

The transition to a sustainable and decarbonized energy system requires substantial investments, supported by a combination of public and private funding mechanisms. These financial instruments are essential to bridge the gap between ambitious climate goals, such as those set by the European Green Deal and Fit for 55 targets, mentioned before, and the practical implementation of renewable energy projects and energy efficiency improvements.

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the key funding programs available across Europe, focusing on their role in enabling the development of RECs and IRECs. The analysis spans European Union initiatives, such as the **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** and the **Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**, as well as national programs tailored to the specific needs of the studied countries.

To simplify the review, funding programs are summarized in tables with the following structure:

- **Name of the project/program:** the official title of the funding mechanism.
- **Implementing agency:** the organization or authority responsible for managing and emitting the fund.
- **Validity period:** the timeline during which the funding mechanism is available.
- **Total Funding Amount (TFA) / Subsidize Amount (SA):** the total allocated budget or the financial aid provided to beneficiaries, such as grants, loans, or co-financing rates
- **Source of funding:** whether the funding is public or private.
- **Description:** a brief explanation of the funding's objectives, eligible activities and key beneficiaries.

This approach provides an overview of the funding mechanisms available for renewable energy and sustainability projects, offering stakeholders insights into financial opportunities and strategies to support the development of industrial energy communities and align with EU climate priorities.

4.1 European Union

Table 4-1 European financial instruments

Name of the project/program	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funding Amount (TFA)/Subsidise amount (SA)	Source of funding)	Description
European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) [27]	European Commission	2021-2027	TFA: €226 billion (including €9 billion for European Territorial Cooperation and €1.9 billion for outermost and sparsely populated regions); SA: co-financing rates 85% for less developed regions, up to 60% for the more developed once.	Public sector	Aims to reduce regional disparities and improve living standards through investments in growth, jobs and European Territorial Cooperation. Focuses on innovation (PO1)(Policy Objective)8, green transition (PO2) and sustainable urban development (8% of resources).
Cohesion Fund [28]	European Commission	2021-2027	TFA: €42.6 billion (€10 billion allocated to the Connecting Europe Facility); SA: co-financing rates up to 85%	Public sector	Supports EU Member States with GNI per capita below 90% of the EU average, focusing on environmental sustainability, renewable energy, circular economy and transport infrastructure. 37% of resources contribute to EU climate objectives.
Just Transition Fund (JTF) [29]	European Commission	2021-2027	TFA: €17.5 billion (€7.5 billion from the Multiannual Financial Framework and €10 billion from NextGenerationEU); SA: co-financing rates 85% for less developed regions, up to 70% for the more developed once.	Public sector	Supports territories affected by the transition to climate neutrality, focusing on economic diversification, professional reskilling, clean energy technologies, emission reduction and industrial site rehabilitation. Includes territorial plans to define specific intervention areas.
Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) [30]	European Commission	2021-2026	TFA: €650 billion (€359 billion in grants and €291 billion in loans)	Public sector	The RRF is the central instrument of NextGenerationEU, designed to support Member States in recovering from the COVID-19 crisis and addressing key challenges. It funds reforms and investments focused on sustainability, resilience and the green and digital transitions. Member States receive grants and loans for projects aligned with EU priorities and specific recommendations under the European Semester. Payments are performance-based, contingent on achieving agreed milestones and targets.

4.2 Italy

Table 4-II Italian financial instruments

Name of the project/program	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funding Amount (TFA)/Subsidise amount (SA)	Source of funding	Description
Mission 2, Component 2, Investment 1.2 (PNRR) [31]	Fund issuer: Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE) Fund manager: GSE	2021 - Until June 30, 2026	TFA: €2.2 billion from the PNRR to achieve at least 2 GW of capacity and 2,500 GWh/year of renewable energy production. SA: Interest-free loans cover up to 100% of eligible costs for the realisation of renewable electricity production facilities.	Public sector	The investment aims at providing support to energy communities, particularly in municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants, to enable the installation of at least 2,000 MW of additional capacity from renewable sources, for an indicative production of 2,500 GWh/year, coupled with energy storage systems. The support is based on interest-free loans of up to 100 % of eligible costs for the realisation of renewable electricity production facilities.
Feed-In Tariff (Tariffa incentivante) [32]	Fund issuer: MASE Fund manager: GSE	From 2021, 20 years from installation	SA: Fixed tariff between €60-€120/MWh, with an additional €10/MWh for photovoltaic installations in specific geographic areas.	Public sector	An incentive tariff for renewable energy produced and virtually self-consumed by members of RECs, calculated and administered by GSE. This tariff promotes local energy self-consumption and encourages the development of renewable energy projects within RECs.
ARERA - valuation fee for self-consumed energy [33]	Fund issuer: MASE Fund manager: ARERA, GSE	2019 - n/a.	SA: Approximately €8/MWh compensation for shared energy, set by ARERA and administered by GSE.	Public sector	Financial compensation for shared renewable energy consumption within RECs. Complements the feed-in tariff and encourages energy sharing within the community, reducing reliance on conventional energy sources.
Beni strumentali – Nuova Sabatini [34]	Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy (MIMIT)	2024 – n/a	SA: Interest subsidy reducing rates to 2.75% for standard investments and 3.575% for Industry 4.0 or environmentally sustainable projects.	Public sector	It is an incentive program aimed at helping SMEs access credit for investing in new machinery, equipment and technologies that enhance operational efficiency and sustainability, including energy transition initiatives. The program supports investments with loans through banks or financial intermediaries (Loans between €20,000 and €4 million), providing affordable financing for up to five years, including a 12-month grace period.

Transition Plans 5.0 [35]	MIMIT	2024-2025	TFA: €12.7 billion budget, including €6.3 billion for energy and digital transformation projects. SA: Tax credit proportional to investments achieving 3-10% energy savings.	Public sector	The "Piano Transizione 5.0" supports the twin transitions of energy and digital transformation, aligning with the REPowerEU strategy. Tax credits are proportional to energy savings achieved through investments: 5% - 15% for investments over €10 million, 15% - 45% for investments below €10 million. Eligible investments include renewable energy systems, digital technologies and staff training (up to 10% of the total investment).
Net Zero Development Contracts [36]	Invitalia	From June 27, 2024 – n/a	TFA: €1.738 billion: €1.225 billion from PNRR Mission M1C2 Investment 7 and €513.77 million from PNRR Mission M2C2 Investment 5.1.	Public sector	Supports industrial development projects and environmental protection initiatives with costs exceeding €20 million. Focuses on manufacturing devices for ecological transition (batteries, solar panels, wind turbines, etc.), key components, and resource recovery for sustainable processes. Funds are granted as capital contributions, soft loans, and direct expense contributions. This program can be instrumental for RECs, especially those formed by companies, as it supports the production and integration of renewable energy systems and components.
Sustainability of Production Processes [37]	Invitalia	From November 11, 2024 – n/a	TFA: €350 million for projects focusing on energy efficiency, renewable energy self-consumption (excluding biomass), and industrial decarbonization. Allocation includes 60% for energy efficiency projects and 40% for southern Italian regions	Public sector	Aims to enhance the sustainability of production processes through renewable energy integration and circular economy practices. At least 60% of the funds are allocated to energy efficiency projects, with 40% reserved for southern Italian regions. This aligns well with REC goals by fostering renewable energy use and reducing environmental impact, making it particularly useful for industrial CERs aiming to integrate self-consumption and improve production sustainability.
Strategic plan 2025 - 2027	Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP)	2025 - 2027	TFA: €81 billion committed, activating €170 billion investments	Public sector	Aims to strengthen Italy's competitiveness, social cohesion, economic security, and a just transition through investments in businesses, public administration, infrastructure, and international cooperation.
Finanziamento Futuro Sostenibile [38]	Unicredit	Ongoing	TFA: Loans starting at €10,000 with interest rate reductions for achieving ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) goals	Private sector	A medium-to-long-term financing solution aimed at supporting businesses committed to improving their sustainability profile. Companies shall select at least two ESG objectives, including one environmental goal. Offers reduced interest rates for achieving measurable ESG performance improvements. Suitable for businesses investing in renewable energy systems, efficient machinery, and sustainable infrastructure.
Finanziamento Business Sostenibile [39]	Banca Sella	Ongoing	TFA: Loans starting at €50,000 tailored to meet ESG goals.	Private sector	Designed for capital companies and social enterprises, excluding micro-enterprises. Offers reduced interest rates upon meeting predefined ESG goals. Focused on supporting businesses in improving sustainability through investments in renewable energy, efficient machinery, and sustainable infrastructure.

S-Loan CER [40]	Intesa Sanpaolo	Ongoing	Tailored financing for projects enhancing energy self-sufficiency, renewable energy systems, and CERs. Offers interest rate reductions for meeting ESG objectives.	Private sector	A specialized product designed to support CER projects, energy self-sufficiency initiatives, and renewable energy system development. Includes ESG-specific targets and reporting, incentivized through reduced interest rates.
Energia Impresa [41]	Intesa Sanpaolo	Ongoing	Financing up to 100% of eligible investments, typically covering 80-100% of the documented costs (excluding VAT).	Private sector	A specialized medium-to-long-term financing solution for businesses investing in renewable energy projects (solar, wind, hydroelectric, biogas, biomethane) or energy efficiency improvements. Loans have a maximum duration of 20 years, with flexible options like fixed or variable interest rates. Designed to support the energy transition, including renewable energy integration and self-consumption initiatives.
Energicamento Business [42]	Crédit Agricole	Ongoing	financing up to 100% of project costs (excluding VAT) with a duration of up to 20 years. Offers flexible disbursement options, including single disbursement or State Advancement Work (SAL) financing.	Private sector	Designed to support investments in renewable energy systems such as photovoltaic, biogas, biomass, wind, hydroelectric, and geothermal energy, as well as energy efficiency projects. Includes flexible repayment terms and aligns investments with revenue from incentives. Loans between €25,000 and €5 million
Finanziamento Green e Sostenibilità [43]	BNL (BNP Paribas Group)	Ongoing	Financing correlated to project investment, with favourable pricing and eligibility for regional and state incentives.	Private sector	Supports projects with positive environmental sustainability impacts, including renewable energy production, energy efficiency, circular economy initiatives, and emission reductions. Includes access to a dedicated Green Desk for tailored guidance.
Investimenti green [44]	BPER bank	Ongoing	Variable, based on project size	Private sector	Green investments focus on sustainable development by supporting renewable resources, energy efficiency, and low-impact processes. Tools include green bonds (e.g., Italy's 2021 BTP Green for ecological transition projects) and ESG funds, which evaluate investments based on environmental, social, and governance criteria. These instruments promote sustainable business practices, resource efficiency, and innovation, aligning financial returns with ethical and ecological values.

4.3 Spain

Table 4-III Spanish & Catalan financial instruments

Name of the project/program	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funding Amount (TFA)/Subsidise amount (SA)	Source of funding	Description
Línea ICO Verde [45]	Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO)	2021 – n/a	TFA: 22.000 M€ SA: Financing up to 100% of project costs for mediation lines and up to 70% for direct loans.	Public sector	The Línea ICO Verde provides up to €22 billion to finance projects for private and public companies and households, aimed at supporting the green transition. It covers projects in sustainable transport, energy efficiency, renewable energy, industrial decarbonization, water management, circular economy, and climate change adaptation. A variety of financial instruments are utilized, including direct loans, mediation lines with banks, debt securities acquisition, and venture capital investments.
ICO Companies and Entrepreneurs [46]	Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO)	2021 – June 2026	TFA: €8.15 billion, with €1 billion reserved for tourism projects and €150 million for university digitization. SA: Financing up to 100% for mediation lines and up to 70% for direct ICO financing.	Public sector	The ICO Companies and Entrepreneurs program supports investment projects for private companies and self-employed individuals within the framework of the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan and the Next Generation EU funds. It offers favourable financing conditions for: -General private companies and self-employed individuals: Investment projects and associated working capital needs. -Tourism sector companies: Projects promoting sustainability, modernization, and the competitiveness of the Spanish tourism industry. -Spanish universities (public and private): Digitalization and artificial intelligence projects that contribute 100% to digital transformation, as outlined in Annex VII of EU Regulation 2021/241. Financing is available through loans or leasing agreements, with fixed or variable interest rates, and repayment terms of 1 to 20 years, including up to 3 years of grace period for principal repayment.
ICF Eco Green	Catalan Institute of Finance (ICF)	Ongoing	For projects with Investments from 500.00€ If financing is included in the program, as a complement to the guarantees provided by the holder, the European Investment Fund will	Public sector.	Loans to promote sustainable investments in the green, circular economy, energy efficiency or climate change mitigation For: Self-employed workers, companies and entities (public or private), energy communities and communities of owners with registered or operational headquarters in Catalonia. https://www.icf.cat/en/productes-financers/prestecs/icf-ecoverda/index.html

			assume, in front of the ICF, 70% of the credit risk plus 90 days of ordinary interest		
BBVA Green Loans (Green Loan) [47]	BBVA	Ongoing	No predefined amount; tailored to project size and scope	Private sector	BBVA Green Loans are financing solutions for companies aiming to fund projects aligned with ESG criteria. Eligible projects include renewable energy, energy efficiency, pollution control, sustainable land and water management, biodiversity conservation, clean transportation, climate adaptation, and circular economy initiatives. Companies shall adhere to the Green Loan Principles (GLP), which require detailed reporting on fund usage, environmental impact evaluation, and external or self-certification of sustainability alignment. Loans can be structured as term loans, revolving credit facilities, or working capital lines.
Santander Green Loans and Bonds [48]	Banco Santander	Ongoing	€114.6 billion in green financing since 2019; tailored loans and bonds for renewable energy and sustainability projects	Private sector	Santander finances renewable energy projects and provides ESG-compliant products, including green loans and bonds. Loans are targeted at renewable energy, energy efficiency, clean transportation, circular economy initiatives, and sustainable agriculture. The Santander Green Bond Framework allocates proceeds to renewable energy loans. Santander collaborates with multilateral institutions like the EIB to provide credit lines for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects. The bank aims to align its portfolio with the Paris Agreement, reduce emissions, and support the green transition globally.
IFEM, financing instruments for innovative enterprises	ICF	Ongoing	Criteria: loan amount between 50.00 and 200.000€. Geographical scope: Catalonia.	Public sector	Convertible participatory loans (participatory loans) to finance seed and start-up companies in co-investment with private investors. Aimed mainly at entrepreneurs or companies in initial phases and first rounds. New, innovative, technological or science-based companies, with high growth potential.
CaixaBank Green Loans [49]	Caixa Bank	Ongoing	Loans for renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainability projects	Private sector	Caixa Bank's Green Loans are designed to support projects with a positive environmental impact, including renewable energy installations (solar, wind), energy efficiency upgrades, and sustainable resource management. These loans are ideal for energy communities as they can fund shared renewable energy systems and efficiency projects within industrial parks, aligning with ESG goals and adhering to Green Loan Principles (GLP).

The Institut Català d'Energia (ICAEN) offers various financial support and funding programs to promote energy efficiency and the adoption of renewable energy sources in Catalonia. These initiatives are designed to assist private individuals, companies, communities of property owners, and local administrations in implementing energy-saving measures.

Additionally, the **PERTE Program (Proyectos Estratégicos para la Recuperación y Transformación Económica)**, which aimed to support strategic projects for economic recovery and transformation with a focus on sustainability and innovation, also came to an end, further limiting current funding options in these areas.

4.4 Austria

Table 4-IV Austrian financial instruments

Name of the project/program	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funding Amount (TFA)/Subsidise amount (SA)	Source of funding	Description
Austrian Climate and Energy Fund for Energy Communities [50]	Klima- und Energiefonds (KPC)	October 7, 2024 – March 31, 2025	Grants for innovative energy community projects and shared generation facilities	Public sector	This program provides financial support for RECs and shared generation facilities, particularly innovative and model projects. Funding includes planning services, environmental studies, training measures, networking activities, and informational events. Eligible participants include individuals, municipalities, legal entities, and SMEs.
Model Projects: Climate-Resilient Transformation in Regions [51]	Klima- und Energiefonds (Climate and Energy Fund)	November 29, 2024 – March 28, 2025	SA: Grants up to €99,000 per project; funding for personnel, materials, and third-party services	Public sector	This program supports regional climate protection and adaptation projects that are innovative and replicable. It is relevant for energy communities (CERs) as it encourages collaboration between stakeholders, including local regions through initiatives such as KEM (Klima- und Energie-Modellregionen), which focuses on reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy, and KLAR! (Klimawandel-Anpassungsmodellregionen), which helps regions adapt to climate change impacts like droughts, floods, and heatwaves. The program focuses on addressing energy poverty, mobility, and sustainable infrastructure. Although investment costs are not supported, the funding can cover essential planning, operational, and implementation costs for CER-related initiatives.
Greenstart Program [52]	Klima- und Energiefonds (Climate and Energy Fund)	November 29, 2024 – February 14, 2025	TFA: €0.8 million; SA: €10,000 for the TOP 10 projects and an additional €20,000 for the TOP 3 projects	Public sector	Supports startups and small organizations with innovative green business ideas focusing on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change. Relevant for energy communities (CERs) looking to integrate innovative solutions, as it provides financial prizes, coaching, workshops, and networking opportunities to advance sustainable energy projects.
Green Finance [53]	Klima- und Energiefonds (Climate and Energy Fund)	Until February 28, 2025 (14:00)	Funding for professional services to improve climate protection project financing	Public sector	Supports SMEs in enhancing the financial feasibility of climate protection projects. Funding covers services such as professional business case development, transparent representation of sustainability aspects, and finance-related communication strategies. Relevant for CERs (Community Energy Renewables) as it aids SMEs in structuring and presenting collaborative renewable energy projects more effectively to attract investments.
Large Storage Systems [54]	Klima- und Energiefonds (Climate and Energy Fund)	Until March 31, 2025	Funding for the design and implementation of innovative energy and heat storage systems	Public sector	Supports innovative energy and heat storage systems for energy communities and industrial applications. Eligible projects include electricity storage systems with a net capacity of more than 1 MWh and heat storage systems with a capacity of 250 MWh or more. Particularly relevant for CERs (Community Energy

					Renewables) aiming to optimize energy supply and efficiency within shared systems.
3rd Financing Call for Photovoltaic and Storage Projects (Cat AD) [55]	EAG Abwicklungsstelle	2024	TFA:€20 million SA: fixed subsidies ranging from €140 to €195/kWp for photovoltaic systems, and €200/kWh for storage	Public sector	Supported the installation of photovoltaic systems and energy storage solutions. Categories ranged from small systems (<10 kWp) to large systems (>100 kWp), encouraging adoption across various scales. Highly relevant for energy communities as it facilitated shared renewable energy production and efficient energy storage systems.

4.5 Czech Republic

Table 4-V Czech financial instruments

Name of the project/program	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funding Amount (TFA)/Subsidise amount (SA)	Source of funding	Description
New Energy Savings [56]	National Development Bank of the Czech Republic (Národní rozvojová banka)	Ongoing	Loan: CZK 0.5 – 60 million (up to 90% of eligible costs); Fixed interest rate: 1.99% p.a.; Grant: up to 35% of project costs; Additional contribution: up to CZK 0.25 million for energy assessment	Private sector	Provides preferential loans for energy-saving projects across the Czech Republic (excluding Prague). Funds are available for insulation, renewable energy installations, energy storage, efficiency upgrades, and waste energy recovery. Projects that meet energy-saving goals may receive grants up to 35% of costs.
Subordinated Loan – NRP [57]	National Development Bank of the Czech Republic (Národní rozvojová banka)	Ongoing	Loan: CZK 1 - 100 million (up to 45% of eligible project costs); Interest rate: 0% - 3%; Maturity: up to 15 years; Grace period: 3 - 5 years	Private sector	Provides preferential subordinated loans for green investments. Projects shall involve a senior loan of equal or greater value from a cooperating financial institution. Eligible expenses include the acquisition of machinery, technology, land, or buildings for business purposes, focusing on renewable energy production, waste management, and climate-friendly activities.
ENERG [58]	National Development Bank of the Czech Republic (Národní rozvojová banka)	Ongoing	Loan: CZK 0.5 - 60 million (up to 70-90% of eligible expenses); Grace period: up to 4 years;	Private sector	Provides interest-free loans for energy-saving projects in Prague. Eligible expenses include insulation, energy-efficient lighting, renewable energy installations, and modernization of energy systems. Projects achieving energy savings receive a 7% financial bonus.

			Interest rate: 0%; Financial contributions: up to CZK 100k for energy assessments, and an additional 7% of the loan amount for achieving energy savings		
Modernisation Fund [59]	State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic	Ongoing	TFA: CZK 500 billion allocated	Public sector	Supports renewable energy projects, modernization of public transport, and sustainable infrastructure development. Highly relevant for energy communities (CERs) aiming to upgrade shared energy systems.
Energy Savings - Energy Savings Challenge II [60] OP TAK (Operational Programme Technologies and Applications for Competitiveness)	MIT (Ministry of industry and trade)	May 24, 2024 - October 31, 2025 (application); Physical completion: October 31, 2026	TFA: CZK 5 billion SA: Eligible project costs: CZK 0.625 – 2 billion per project Support intensity: 50–80% for small enterprises. 40–70% for medium enterprises. 30–60% for large enterprises.	Public sector	Provides grants for reducing energy intensity and emissions through renewable energy installations, energy storage, energy efficiency upgrades, green roofs, and waste energy recovery. Support ranges from 30-80%, based on project specifics.
Green Loan [61]	Komerční banka (BK)	Ongoing	Komerční banka offers preferential interest rates	Private sector	Provides funding for projects with positive environmental impacts, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, pollution reduction, clean mobility, sustainable water and waste management, circular economy, and energy-efficient buildings. The loan requires documentation of the environmental benefits of the project and aligns with international green financing methodologies.

4.6 Alternative sources of financing

The evolution towards a more sustainable energy system requires innovative financial models that go beyond traditional banking credit channels. Among the emerging options, tools like **crowdfunding**, **crowdlending**, and other forms of direct citizen financing are gaining increasing relevance. These financing mechanisms offer a participatory and inclusive approach, mobilizing resources from a broad base of supporters, such as citizens, businesses and private investors, and promoting:

- **Community participation:** involving beneficiaries directly in decision-making and financial processes.
- **Financial accessibility:** reducing dependence on traditional credit institutions and expanding funding opportunities for local projects.
- **Economic sustainability:** creating a diversified economic support base for renewable energy initiatives.

Crowdfunding represents a fundraising method that allows financing projects through contributions from multiple parties via online platforms. This model is articulated in various types, including donation-based crowdfunding for social projects, reward-based crowdfunding offering symbolic or material rewards and equity crowdfunding, which allows raising capital by offering investors shares in the promoting company or project.

Crowdlending, on the other hand, provides a structure that enables companies to obtain financing from a group of investors who receive interest on the capital lent. This model is particularly effective for projects with predictable returns, offering defined yields and adaptability across different scales.

The integration of these tools into renewable energy projects not only broadens funding opportunities, but also strengthens local community engagement, making the energy transition more inclusive and sustainable.

In the Czech Republic, crowdfunding for RECs is still in its emerging phase. Currently, there are no platforms specifically dedicated to this sector in the country. However, there are generic crowdfunding platforms operating in the Czech Republic that could be utilized to finance energy projects.

Table 4-VI Alternative source of finance

Name of the project/program	State	Implementing agency	Validity period	Total Funds Raised	Source of funding	Description
Ener2Crowd [62]	Italy	Ener2Crowd Srl	Ongoing	Over €34 million raised; average annual return between 6-10%; lending and equity crowdfunding models	Private sector	A crowd investing platform authorized by CONSOB and the Bank of Italy, operating under the European ECSP Regulation. It offers investment opportunities in 100% green projects focused on renewable energy, CO2 reduction, and sustainability. It includes lending initiatives (loans with interest) and equity (purchasing company shares). Projects certify environmental impacts and support reforestation, financial literacy, and cultural awareness initiatives.
Produzioni dal Basso [63]	Italy	Produzioni dal Basso Srl	Ongoing	Over €28 million raised; 9,516 projects funded; 471,197 registered users	Private sector	The first Italian crowdfunding platform, offering three modes: "collect everything," "simple donation," and "all or nothing." It supports artistic, cultural, social, and entrepreneurial projects. Fees range from 3% to 5% per transaction.
Ceress - REC Crowdfunding [64]	Italy	Ceress Srl	Ongoing	Variable, based on project; investment grants proportional returns from energy community profits	Private sector	Ceress enables individuals and businesses to invest in renewable energy projects through crowdfunding. The funds collected are used to build and operate renewable energy plants within energy communities, with investors receiving a share of the profits proportional to their contribution. Open to all, regardless of space, capital, or technical expertise.

Crowdfundme - Energia Democratica [65]	Italy	Energia Democratica Società Cooperativa	Ongoing	Target: €520,000 - €875,000; Annual returns 6-8% for up to 30 years	Private sector	Energia Democratica uses equity crowdfunding to finance shared photovoltaic systems. Investors receive dividends and benefit from capital gains, with potential total returns up to 4x the initial investment. The cooperative's structure democratizes energy ownership and supports renewable energy production, stabilizing energy costs and enabling participation in energy communities.
Enerfip [66]	Itlay, Spain	Enerfip S.A.S.	Ongoing	Over €599 million financed; annual returns up to 9.5%; 494 sustainable projects financed in 11 years	Private sector	Enerfip is a regulated crowdfunding platform approved by the AMF (Autorité des Marchés Financiers). It offers competitive and transparent investment opportunities starting from €10. Investors can choose projects in renewable energy sectors such as solar, wind, bioenergy, and hydrogen, among others, while reducing their carbon footprint and avoiding investments in fossil fuels or speculative finance.
Ecrowd! [67]	Spain	Ecrowd S.A.	Ongoing	Over €10.3 million in loans; minimum investment from €50; supports projects in energy, water, education, health, and circular economy	Private sector	Ecrowd! is a crowdlending platform focused on generating positive societal and environmental impacts. It finances viable, productive projects with a transparent and accessible process, offering fair returns to investors. The platform emphasizes sustainability, with projects avoiding 130,653 metric tons of CO2 annually, and targets diverse sectors like renewable energy, mobility, and community development. Applicable to both private or public sector.
Flobers [68]	Spain	Flobers S.A.	Ongoing	Up to €5 million per project; crowdlending and crowdfunding options available	Private sector	Flobers is a Spanish platform regulated by the CNMV (Comisión Nacional del Mercado de Valores), focusing on sustainable and impactful projects in renewable energy, social economy, water management, and sustainable business. It evaluates and finances small and medium-sized projects contributing to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, ensuring solvency, stable cash flows, and measurable positive impact.
Crowd4Climate [69]	Austria	klimja GmbH	Ongoing	Funding volume from €250,000 to €2 million; loan terms 3-7 years; market-aligned interest rates	Private sector	Crowd4Climate (klimja) is a platform focusing on climate protection and renewable energy projects. It supports projects with a proven business model and clear ecological, economic, and social returns. The platform provides professional support throughout the process, from due diligence to campaign management, offering loans without requiring equity or voting rights. Open to projects in Austria, Germany, and selectively in high-development-potential countries globally.

4.7 Financing barriers and opportunities

The analysis of financing mechanisms across European Union reveals barriers and opportunities in supporting the development of IRECs. While funding programs are all fully align with the EU's goals for decarbonization and energy transition, their accessibility, scope, and implementation vary significantly, reflecting differences in regional priorities, economic contexts, and financial strategies.

Despite existing barriers, several opportunities can enhance the effectiveness of financing mechanisms for renewable energy projects and IRECs and could accelerate the development of sustainable energy systems and ensure that financial mechanisms deliver equitable and impactful results across EU.

Opportunities

1. **Alternative financing mechanisms like crowdlending** and equity crowdfunding offers a promising avenue to democratize access to funding while fostering greater community engagement. These approaches not only mobilize diverse financial resources but also encourage local participation in the energy transition.
2. **The ESCO model based on guaranteed savings** represents an opportunity for financing investments with support from the ESCO company and the advantage of visualizing savings.
3. **Tailored financial programs** can be set starting on ongoing ones to support high-power capacity IRECs, including energy storage solutions and collaborative initiatives that are align with industrial energy community goals.
4. **European-Level Programs:** initiatives like the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and the Just Transition Fund (JTF) provide substantial resources to support renewable energy projects, particularly in regions and sectors undergoing significant economic transformation. Their focus on green transitions and regional development is crucial for enabling large-scale renewable energy deployment.
5. **Capacity-building initiatives** enhance IREC groups to better leverage available resources, contributing to a broader and more inclusive energy transition, contributing to effectively enabling the IREC environment.
6. **With a focus on Italy,** it demonstrates a strong commitment to supporting renewable energy through diverse financial instruments, including incentives for energy communities, support for local self-consumption and funding for industrial and technological innovation. These mechanisms are tailored to both small municipalities and larger-scale projects.
7. **With a focus on Spain,** it provides a well-structured framework of financial mechanisms that foster renewable energy adoption, industrial decarbonization and energy efficiency. Its programs encourage local participation and focus on leveraging public and private investments to achieve sustainability goals.
8. **With a focus on Austria,** it emphasizes innovation and collaboration through grants for model projects and energy communities, particularly those focused on climate resilience.
9. **With a focus on Czech Republic,** it provides accessible financing for energy-saving projects, offering low-interest loans and grants that incentivize renewable energy adoption and efficiency improvements.

Barriers

Several barriers persist across the analysed countries, limiting the effectiveness and reach of financing mechanisms:

1. **Main focus on small-scale projects:** most programs prioritize residential and small community projects, leaving industrial parks and larger-scale initiatives underfunded.
2. **Administrative complexity:** accessing funds often requires navigating complex bureaucratic processes, which discourage participation, particularly for SMEs and energy communities. Thus, simplifying administrative processes remains a key priority, as reducing bureaucratic obstacles can significantly increase participation, particularly among SMEs and local stakeholders.
3. **Regional and economic disparities:** while some countries offer comprehensive support (e.g. Italy and Spain), the others face gaps in program design and implementation, especially in less economically developed regions.
4. **Investment risks:** regulatory changes, high initial costs and long payback periods pose challenges for private investors, slowing down large-scale adoption of renewable energy projects.
5. **Limited crowdfunding options:** emerging financial models, such as crowdfunding, are well-developed in certain regions (e.g. Italy) but remain nascent or unavailable in others, like the Czech Republic.
6. **Greater EU-level coordination** is desired to harmonize strategies across Member States, reducing regional disparities and enhancing the overall efficiency of funding mechanisms.

5 Business models – preliminary assessment

This section provides a preliminary assessment of potential business models (BMs) relevant to the ENERGIZE framework. While the analysis at this stage aims to identify broad categories of models applicable to IRECs, a detailed exploration incorporating stakeholders' inputs will be presented in **Deliverable D2.4**. This iterative approach ensures that the final models are robust, context-specific, and aligned with stakeholder priorities. This phased approach ensures that the BMs are not only theoretically sound but also practically implementable, addressing the unique requirements of pilot local stakeholders.

5.1 Preliminary business models description

1. BM1 – IREC ownership to Industrial Park members: Companies within an industrial park collectively own and manage renewable energy assets and energy efficiency project, sharing costs, benefits, and responsibilities to produce and self-consume energy from renewable energy to reduce carbon emissions
2. BM2 – IREC ownership to ESCo: Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) finance and implement efficiency upgrades or renewable energy systems, recouping costs through savings achieved over time.
3. BM 3 – IREC ownership to REC: Residents and public actors actively participate to finance through innovative financial mechanisms (Section 4.7) to collectively share asset management and electricity between members
4. BM4 – IREC for flexibility services: technological innovation with remote sensor could be an opportunity for balancing and schedule industrial loads. Local DSOs and TSOs could benefit substantially from the local flexibility offered by IRECs that have become pivotal actors in the energy sector.

Each model is briefly described below, outlining its core function, how it works, and potential benefits for its members participating in ENERGIZE project. While this analysis identifies key characteristics and potential applications, it represents an initial step.

Stakeholder consultation is a crucial process for engaging interested parties in decision-making and defines the most suitable legal form based on each member state. ENERGIZE could understand which governance and business legal models are available for each pilot country. Municipal or citizens' participation in such processes can be limited due to factors like higher technical involvement or resource constraints. ESCOs could play a vital role in energy-related projects, and their collaboration with different governance frameworks for IREC can be instrumental in achieving shared objectives. Ultimately, a nation's specific rules and regulations significantly influence stakeholder engagement, organizational structures, and the impact of private developers and public associations.

Table 5-1 BM1 description

BM1 – IREC ownership to Industrial Park members
BM1 In a nutshell
<p>Each member of the IREC invests in a renewable plant, that is installed within its own industrial parks that leads to (i) energy efficiency with self-consumption and carbon emission minimization and (ii) enter the energy market for selling excess electricity. The member owns the surface area and technical asset (e.g. renewables plants and energy consumption infrastructure), and it operates and maintains the technological asset with the support of internal staff trained in collective energy management for the IREC. BM1 is suitable for industrial associations or group of medium-large enterprises.</p>
Overview
<p>BM1 fully addresses the challenges of a sustainable economy, the efficiency exploitation of natural resources (solar, wind, water, etc..) and the high demand for a reliable electricity supply for enterprises.</p> <p>It embraces the cooperative approach while balancing the three components, with a special focus on (i) the efficient use of the natural resource (e.g. water, energy, production material) (ii) energy efficiency of industrial production to minimize waste (iii) clean energy generation to reduce carbon emissions from fossil fuels, thus enhancing energy security. This type of model is highly replicable and scalable, making it suitable for different sizes of industrial actors and a large variety of energy patterns.</p> <p>Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM1 could consist of different mechanism such as: (i) grant financing (in form of progress-based grant and technical assistance), (ii) microfinancing for industrial association, (iii) commercial loans for medium-large enterprise and (iv) junior debt.</p>
How it works
<p>BM1 is to implement by an Industrial Park member (either industrial association or a medium-large enterprise) that wants to install a renewable plant on its own facility or available land. Three asset clusters characterize BM1: (i) renewable power generation plants, (ii) systems and personnel for energy management, and (iii) available surfaces. All three asset clusters are owned by the same entity, which is also responsible for their operation within an integrated business model. Technical support for energy management is required to assure the business sustainability. The business objective is to diversify the revenue streams and enable energy sales in the market.</p> <p>Key partners include (i) public financing entities able to support capital costs through de-risking financing mechanisms, (ii) private financing institutions, (iii) technology providers, which can be categorized into renewable technology suppliers and smart meter providers.</p>
Reference project in operation for the BM1
<p>Scientific literature classifies this model such as an “energy cooperative” [70] or “bottom-up model” [71]. BM1 proposes IRECs in terms of general project governance, key stakeholders, and a shared community-based approach.</p>

Table 5-II BM2 description

BM2 – IREC ownership to ESCo
BM2 In a nutshell
<p>An ESCo invests in and installs renewable plants within industrial parks, providing comprehensive energy services including audits, building improvements, and energy management. With the support of trained staff, the ESCo owns and operates both temporary surface rights and technical assets (renewable plants and energy consumption equipment). This model fosters a dual community - both physical and interest-based - making it ideal for industrial associations and groups of medium-large enterprise seeking integrated energy solutions with reduced technical burden.</p>
Overview
<p>BM2 fully addresses the financial burden faced by enterprises. Unlike conventional technology vendors or energy consultants, an ESCo can finance energy systems, and its compensation is typically based on the energy savings achieved by its clients.</p> <p>Several variations of this business model can be leveraged. In addition to developing energy generation systems, community ESCo can offer building retrofits and energy-efficient equipment (e.g. air conditioners and electric water heaters). By offering these services, ESCo guarantees additional energy savings for their clients, securing their revenue streams, as they are compensated based on the actual energy saving achieved.</p> <p>Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM2 could consist of alternative revenues stream, such reimbursements schemes or fringe benefits for employees.</p>
How it works
<p>BM2 is implemented by an ESCo that seeks to install a renewable plant on IREC land. Under BM2, revenues generated for industrial park members - such as energy savings - can be shared between the ESCo and its customers in different ways and used to reimburse ESCo of their investments. In some Member-States, ESCo are also exploring combined power and heat solutions.</p> <p>In all cases, the energy operator supplies the technical know-how in both situations, helping to scale the initiative. Depending on the level of investment and the chosen business model, incentives can be allocated between the energy operator and the industrial park members.</p> <p>ESCo payment plans typically include (i) guaranteed savings, the ESCo commits to provide specific energy savings, and (ii) shared savings, which are distributed over a set period according to a pre-established agreement between the ESCo and its clients.</p>
Reference project in operation for the BM2
<p>Relevant examples include “solar-as-a-service” and “heat-as-service”, where community ESCo finance PV systems or heating district infrastructure while managing installation, upstream supply, and maintenance. This BM enables end-users to become prosumers [72-74]. Scientific literature classifies this model such as a “community ESCo” [70] or “energy operator model” [71].</p>

Table 5-III BM3 description

BM3 – IREC ownership to REC
BM3 In a nutshell
<p>A REC led by citizens and public entities, invests and installs renewable plants within industrial parks, providing comprehensive energy services including audits, building improvements, waste recovery and energy management. With the support of trained staff, the REC owns and operates the technical assets (renewable plants and energy consumption equipment), enabling energy efficiency through self-consumption and market participation via excess electricity sales. The model fosters a dual community - both physical and interest-based - making it ideal for industrial associations and public administrations seeking integrated energy solutions for their territories.</p>
Overview
<p>BM3 fully addresses the challenge of sustainable territories, optimizing the use of natural resources (solar, wind, water, etc..) and meeting the high demand of reliable electricity supply from enterprises.</p> <p>Prosumer-focused REC are typically local communities established by prosumers, who act as investors, customers, and decision-makers. They collaborate to leverage special financing terms when purchasing assets or buying energy in bulk.</p> <p>Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM3 could consist of different mechanism such as: (i) crowdfunding initiatives (ii) loans (iii) grant for social inclusive projects that could benefit local associations and cooperatives focused on specific initiatives (e.g. public transportation, water management).</p>
How it works
<p>IREC prosumers can pool their resources and aggregate demand by participating in REC, allowing them to gain greater negotiating power with energy retailers and suppliers. This is one of the primary advantages of this BM. However, successful implementation requires agreement from all stakeholders, as well as technological and physical infrastructures capable of supporting and monitoring energy, financial, and information transactions for billing purposes.</p> <p>The involvement of key partners — such as industrial park managers, resident businesses, local authorities, and financing bodies — is essential for tailoring and implementing effective BMs. Their inputs ensure that the proposed models: (i) address specific energy needs and challenges (ii) align with local socio-economic and regulatory contexts (iii) enhance long-term viability through stakeholder buy-in.</p>
Reference project in operation for the BM3
<p>Scientific references refer to as “community prosumerism” [70] or “top-down approach” [71]. Additionally, project deliverable D2.3 provides examples of public-private partnership. The ENERGIZE BM3 model aims to overcome common barriers such as mistrust, regulatory complexity, and imbalance resource allocation, fostering more inclusive and sustainable energy systems. BM3 propose IRECs as a framework for general project collaboration and a shared community-based approach.</p>

Table 5-IV BM4 description

BM4 – IREC for flexibility services
BM4 In a nutshell
An IREC for flexibility services acts as a community aggregator, installing smart energy systems and renewables within a defined community. It provides comprehensive energy management platforms for all members. By aggregating member flexibility, the IREC enables participation in local energy markets, creating new revenue streams for members that accept demand-side managements or production flexibility actions (e.g. load shifting and peak shaving).
Overview
<p>In BM4 IREC acts as flexibility aggregation, enabling small and medium enterprises to participate in energy markets by pooling their demand and production flexibility. Individual consumers often lack the resources and scale to meet market requirements, but aggregation addresses this barrier.</p> <p>Community aggregators, operating either locally or at the power system level, contract with members to provide flexibility through changes in energy consumption patterns with direct or indirect control. These contracts may involve (i) dispatchable programs (e.g. direct load control) (ii) non-dispatchable programs (e.g. dynamic pricing). Aggregators provide the necessary technology (smart meters, energy management systems, etc.) and manage the complexity of market participation. Members benefit from reduced energy bills and potential new revenue streams through flexibility trading. Aggregators profit from their role in market participation.</p> <p>These "communities of interest" can be initiated by aggregators or end-users, with end-users actively involved in decision-making through contractual agreements. Successful aggregation depends on (i) robust ICT infrastructure, (ii) supportive regulatory frameworks, and (iii) effective alignment of interests among IREC members.</p>
How it works
<p>BM4 is implemented by an Industrial Park group that wants to offer energy flexibility by adjusting production schedules across different time horizons. BM4 consist of three key asset clusters: (i) renewable power generation plant, (ii) systems and labour for energy management and flexibility services and (iii) available load that could be shifted/adjusted. All the three asset clusters are owned and controlled by the same entity, who is also committed to operate them in a kind of integrated business.</p> <p>Key partners include (i) industrial park members, (ii) technology providers (including renewable energy and smart meter suppliers) and (iii) national authorities, such as distribution system operators (DSOs) which facilitate local flexibility market or peer-to-peer training between members.</p>
Reference project in operation for the BM1
Scientific references classify this model as a "community flexibility aggregator" [70]. ENERGIZE BM4 can overcome key social barriers such as concerns over data privacy and trust, regulatory complexity and lack of knowledge about flexibility services and market participation.

6 Conclusions

The ENERGIZE project represents a significant step towards sustainable energy transition in European industrial sectors. By implementing innovative cooperative models, the project has demonstrated that IRECs can be an effective solution for reducing carbon emissions and improving energy efficiency within industrial parks.

The review of the regulatory framework and financial mechanisms highlighted both strengths and gaps within the European context and individual Member States (Italy, Spain, Czech Republic and Austria). While current regulations and incentives are strongly oriented towards supporting the energy transition, they often favour small-scale configurations and leave room for improvement in supporting large-scale initiatives within industrial parks.

Greater regulatory harmonisation across European countries could facilitate the adoption of cooperative models on a larger scale, reducing disparities in access to incentives and simplifying administrative requirements. In addition, targeted financial instruments tailored to the specific needs of industrial parks could accelerate the energy transition by promoting solutions such as energy storage and shared resource management.

The preliminary assessment identified four business models for IRECs within ENERGIZE: industry-owned, ESCo-operated, community-owned, and flexibility service-based. An iterative approach ensures their robustness, adaptability, and alignment with key stakeholder priorities, fostering replicability and scalability in industrial energy cooperation.

To maximise the impact of energy transition initiatives, it will be crucial to continue fostering cooperation between stakeholders, investing in advanced technological tools and strengthening institutional support. These elements will help ensure greater replicability of the models and consolidate the results achieved, inspiring other industrial sectors to follow similar paths.

The ENERGIZE project thus provides a solid foundation for further exploring the potential of industrial energy communities, with the aim of turning industrial parks into tangible examples of sustainability and energy innovation.

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